

**Modelling public-private-partnerships
in
Indian emergency medical services
applying game theory**

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Abstract

Governments across the world have been preferring public-private-partnerships (PPP) over traditional methods in the past few decades to procure public services for their citizens. Developing countries, like India has the potential to successfully deploy PPP in providing integrated emergency medical services (EMS) like that of the west. This paper provides a base for implementing PPP contractual mechanism, when the government needs to maximize its social surplus or value for money (VFM). Further, the study attempts to observe the relationship between three players in a multiple principal agent model where government and global investor act as the principals and the service providers acts as the agents. This study intends to portray the equilibrium contract set among the three players including analysing moral hazard problems, signalling aspects, incentivization and matching through the entire contract cycle.

Key words: Contracts, Game theory, Emergency medical services (EMS), Moral Hazard, Matching, PPP, Signalling

Introduction

One of the innovative ways, in which developing countries like India is managing to provide integrated emergency medical services (EMS) across all of its 29 states is to involve an extended use of private service providers through public-private partnership (PPP) contract mechanisms (KPMG, n.d.). Despite a large set of definitions of PPP's existing across the world today, PPP can be simply be defined as an agreement between a single or multiple private partners (Builders and operators) and the government (Ross & Yan, 2015), so that government's servicing objectives are aligned with the objectives of private service providers (for-profit or private organisations and not-for-profit (NFP) or non-governmental organisations (NGOs)). While PPP has advantages such as the private service providers compete among themselves to operate at low costs and higher efficiencies thereby finding innovations to address social needs, the flexibility to meet changing demands due to long contractual periods would be a major limitation (Raman, Björkman, & Björkman, 2008). Also, substantial evidence (Liu, Hotchkiss, & Bose, 2007) has shown that intervention by the government to contract out to private service providers (SP) has a positive effect on access and equity. Though, same cannot be said about its effects on quality and efficiency. Thus, apart from the PPP's, a start-up private service provider of emergency medical services can also look up-to Global investors in healthcare industry, who focus only on Return of Investment (ROI).

Further, in this study we will be examining the relationship between a private start-up service provider's social entrepreneur, the government which acts as an angel and the global investor whose role is similar to that of a venture capitalist after a seed investment has been made by the government (angel). (Elitzur & Gaviious, 2003)

In the current model, we have tried to address and illustrate a trade-off between the above -mentioned conflicting situations by considering and developing a setup among the three risk-neutral players involved in the game. Also, an objective function that is preferred i.e. (Ross & Yan, 2015)

- 1) Minimizing the cost to the consumers (emergency patients) and
- 2) Maximizing the total social surplus need to be considered in order to come up with a trade-off. In this study our aim is also to try and come up with equilibrium contract among the player, thereby providing insights into the contractual arrangement.

Finally, an attempt will be made to analyse moral hazard problem between service provider and global investor, as both tend to display certain opportunistic characteristics in the choices that they make and get insights to what situations it can lead to and how they can be improved. Also, other aspects like signalling, incentivization and matching games which occur through different phases of contract cycle will be considered.

General Model

Basic setup

The setting in our study involves a start-up service provider with a risk neutral social entrepreneur, government whose role is similar to that of angel and provides advisory services as well as that of seed capital financing as well as operating expenses, and the global investor whose role is similar to that of a venture capitalist. (Elitzur & Gaviious, 2003)

The above approach can be considered as a multi principal- multiple agent model (Attar, Campioni, Piaser, & Rajan, 2006), where the government is considered as the principal along with the global investor and the service provider is considered as the agent.

The gross social benefit of the PPP, which cannot be specified by the contract and according to the government, which is Value for money (VFM) is given by

$$u_i = \{u_L, u_H\} \text{ where } u_H > u_L > 0 \text{ (Ross \& Yan, 2015)}$$

VFM in this context is the utility of service that is obtained at a necessary quality by the consumers of EMS (patients) at the lowest cost with the desired access, equity and efficiencies. (Oliveira Cruz & Cunha Marques, 2014)

If the government has estimated the specifications i.e. demand accurately, then the social benefits would be u_H . However, there is a probability p that the government may have provided wrong specifications in the initial contract or certain situations i.e. technological changes has brought in undue change in the nature of services (Lee & Kim, 2018). In such cases renegotiation by the service provider with the government occurs and hence a new contract design will restore the u_H benefits.

However, if renegotiation is not possible, the lower benefit u_L may be realized. In order to avoid the realization of lower benefits u_L , the service provider enters into a relationship with the global investor which acts as the venture capitalist. The government would decide on certain portions of the share that would enable to finally obtain a maximum social surplus when the global investor exits.

Timeline

The sequence in timing of the events is given in Figure 1. The explanation is as follows

Once the government has selected the service provider for the EMS contract by providing P_0 as the capital and operating expenses investment, with the necessary quality of services the social entrepreneur decides on exerting an effort e_0 which is observed only by him/her. As effort is assumed to be a cost for the social entrepreneur, we can denote it by $C(e)$.

The SP's cost depends on the effort it exerts. An assumption that is been made here is that effort is not contractible, i.e. effort 's value need not be shown to a court or any mechanisms that enforce contracts.

If S be the cost of material, labour, operations etc., e be the effort or the innovative ways the SP choses to operate and Δ be the marginal productivity of effort than (Ross & Yan, 2015) studies indicates that

$$C(e) = S - \Delta * e, \text{ where } \Delta > 0.$$

Here Δ is the SP's private information and hence not known by the government or the global investor. (i.e. *ex ante*) (Bettignies & Ross, 2004). Further, if the variable costs such as disutility costs is also a function of effort and can be represented by $\varphi(e)$.

Then assuming that the SP's outcome is non-taxable considering that it is non-profit firm

VFM which is related to Cash-out of the service provider is given by

$$\varphi = \pi(P, e) - C(e) - \varphi(e)$$

Where $\pi(P, e)$ is the cash-out (i.e. revenue of the service provider).

If there is no change in nature or demand, then the outcome u_H i.e. maximum VFM needs to be realized.

If due to nature demand changes and renegotiation happens with government, which it accepts with switching costs s , the P_0 is changed to P_1 and VFM u_H is realized.

However, if renegotiation is not possible, then SP enters into a relationship with Global investor who invests I. Since the government has played the role of angel by investing initially, it would set up α , β , which are the shares retained by the social entrepreneur (after the investor's shared part) and investor leaving the government with a share of $(1-\alpha)(1-\beta)$ and the cash-out of the service provider is given by the function $\pi(P, e, I)$ (Elitzur & Gavius, 2011)

0. Start-up EMS Service Provider (SP) is found.
1. SP bid for PPP Government Contract.
2. Government Selects SP and Provides P_0 as the initial capital & operating expenses for delivering at a particular QOS, access, efficiency and equity
3. SP chooses to reject or accept.
4. If SP accepts, Social entrepreneur executes effort e_0
5. Nature changes demand - if no change, go to 4.
6. SP renegotiate using bargaining principles with Government.
7. Government accepts or rejects
8. If Government accepts, design changed with both parties incurring switching costs s , P_0 renegotiated to P_1 .
if rejects, go to 12.
9. Social entrepreneur now executes with new effort e_1 .
10. The Outcome i.e. value for money (VFM) is realized
11. The contract is executed
12. SP invokes Global Investor's funds. Global Investor decides on Investment I. Government determines α , and β , the shares that are retained by Social entrepreneur (after the global investor has retained his share) and Global Investor.
13. Social entrepreneur exerts an effort e_1 .
14. Exit Value is Social surplus.

Figure 1 - Timeline

Summary

The summary of the game is given in the tables below

Player	Strategic Decision	Share (Situation1)	Pay off (Situation 1)
Service Provider	e	α	$\alpha * \pi(P, e) - C(e)$
Government	P, α , β	$(1-\alpha)$	$(1-\alpha)\pi(P, e) - (1+\lambda_1) * P$
Global Investor	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 1

Player	Strategic Decision	Share (Situation 2)	Pay off (Situation 2)
Service Provider	e	α	$\alpha * \pi(P, e) - C(e)$
Government	P, α , β	$(1 - \alpha)$	$(1 - \alpha)\pi(P, e) - (1 + \lambda_2) * P$
Global Investor	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 2

Player	Strategic Decision	Share (Situation 3)	Pay off (Situation 3)
Service Provider	e	$\alpha * (1 - \beta)$	$\alpha * (1 - \beta) * \pi(P, e, I) - C(e)$
Government	P, α , β	$(1 - \alpha) * (1 - \beta)$	$(1 - \alpha) * (1 - \beta) * \pi(P, e, I) - (1 + \lambda_3) * P$
Global Investor	I	β	$\beta * \pi(P, e, I) - (1 + \eta) * I$

Table 3

In the summary as shown in Table 1, there are three situations. Situation 1 is when the desired outcome is achieved, without any changes in demand. Situation 2 happens when there is change that occurs due to nature, and renegotiation happens between government and social entrepreneur. Situation 3 occurs when renegotiation between government and social entrepreneur does not work out and the role of Global Investor comes into picture. The payoffs have been stated.

We assume the following for the three situations

$$\pi(0, e, 0) = \pi(P, 0, 0) = 0$$

$$\pi(0, e, 0) = \pi(P, 0, 0) = 0$$

$$\pi(0, e, I) = \pi(P, 0, I) = \pi(P, e, 0) = 0$$

These assumptions imply that in situation 1 and 2, the VFM is zero when the SP does not exert any effort e or the government does not invest in capital and operating expenses P when the global investor does not come into picture. The final assumption implies that in situation 3, when the social entrepreneur does not exert an effort e or government or global investor does not invest P or I respectively, the social surplus becomes zero and the government has to go for rebidding. Here $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ are the specific rate of investment that is taken into account by the government and η is the specific rate of return on I taken into account by the global investor.(Elitzur & Gavius, 2003)

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